

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CONCOMITANT SOMATIC PATHOLOGY OF PATIENTS WITH HERNIAS OF THE LUMBAR SPINE IN DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TREATMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE

Sultonov A.

*Neurosurgeon, department of neurosurgery, multidisciplinary clinic,
Tashkent Medical Academy, Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-8664-5939>*

Rakhimbaeva G.

Head of the Department of Nervous Diseases of the Tashkent Medical Academy, Republic of Uzbekistan

Mirzaev A.

*Deputy Director for Personnel and Administrative Issues,
JSC "NMMC" MA "Kyzyl-Kum", Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8216-54>*

Abstract

The article of data on the effectiveness of modern methods of treatment of intervertebral hernias of the lumbar spine is presented. Historical aspects of the development of spinal neurosurgery, the main methods of surgical treatment. This publication presents the main methods of surgical treatment of herniated intervertebral disc, characterizes the positive and negative aspects of each method. A differentiated approach to the treatment of intervertebral disc herniations in the lumbar spine. Assessment of quality of life and pain syndrome using questionnaires. Determining the effectiveness of surgical treatment and the impact on the quality of life of patients.

Keywords: diagnostics, herniated disc, surgical treatment, conservative treatment, differentiated an approach.

Relevance

The causes of intervertebral disc herniation according to literature data can be different in their origin due to inflammatory processes, physical activity, trauma, etc. Currently, in developed countries, intervertebral disc herniation most often occurs due to low mobility and sedentary lifestyle of people. According to world statistics, a huge number of people suffer from osteochondrosis with back pain - over 80% of the world's population [1,6,7,10,11]. Osteochondrosis with back pain according to literature data is quite common, in the population it is 58-84% of patients, and the incidence is 4-33% per year [1,4,7,12,10].

The incidence rates of osteochondrosis with back pain in different countries of the world can be different, the more developed the country, the more patients. With osteochondrosis of the spine, intervertebral disc herniation is a common cause of lower back pain. In this case, the pain in the lower back, localized in the back area, is limited from above by the twelfth rib, and from below by the lower gluteal folds [6,7,12].

For example, according to literary data, the incidence of chronic back pain in osteochondrosis of the spine among adults is determined to be 26-33% of the total number of neurological patients in the population [7,12].

At present, the issue of surgical tactics and a differentiated approach to the treatment of intervertebral disc herniations at the level of the lumbar spine remains not fully resolved.

Depending on the method of treatment, further rehabilitation of patients depends. In some cases, when a fixing system is installed on the spine, the rehabilitation period may be extended due to long-term

consolidation, and accordingly, the quality of life of patients suffers longer [3,4,5, 9,12,13,14,15,16,17].

At the modern stage of development of medicine since the active use of MRI and MSCT in the practice of neurosurgeons, it became possible to assess various pathologies of the intervertebral disc pathology through radiation diagnostics. Subsequently, the use of electroneuromyography (ENGM) made it possible to determine the level of damage to the nerve root, making it possible to determine the tactics of surgical treatment [2,7,18].

Currently, the quality of life is assessed by various scales and questionnaires. For a full-fledged study of the quality of life of patients, it is of great importance to assess the overall quality of life, the quality of life by disease and symptom of the disease [8,12,16].

Purpose of the study: to improve the treatment results of patients with lumbar spine hernias by using differentiated treatment tactics with an assessment of the quality of life.

Material and methods

The study is based on the results of observations of 165 patients with lumbar pain who were treated in the hospital of the Tashkent Medical Academy, a multidisciplinary clinic, and the neurosurgery department in the period from 2019 to 2023.

To establish a diagnosis and select a treatment method, all patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including clinical, neurological and instrumental research methods.

During the initial examination of patients, as the main criteria for lumbar osteochondrosis (LO), attention was paid to the presence of the following symptoms - unilateral or, in rare cases, bilateral pain in the lumbar region radiating to the leg; the presence of

sensitivity disorders in the innervation zone of any roots of the lumbar vertebrae; the presence of such symptoms as hypertonicity of the lumbar muscles due to pain syndrome; limited movement due to pain syndrome or paresis of the limbs; atrophy of the leg muscles in the innervation zone of the roots of the lumbar vertebrae were also checked.

An important place in establishing a diagnosis and determining further treatment tactics was given to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data from 1.5 to 3.0 Tesla, MSCT and digital X-ray research methods.

In our studies, we used electroneuromyography (ENMG), which determines the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail, with a reliability of 75%, giving us the opportunity to choose the tactics of surgical or conservative treatment of lumbar pain syndrome in osteochondrosis of the spine.

In our studies, to assess the quality of life of patients, we used questionnaires: European Quality of Life Questionnaire Euro Qol-5D and a visual analogue scale (VAS) to determine the intensity of pain. After diagnosis, all patients were subjected to surgical intervention or conservative treatment by determining the tactics of increasing the radicality of the pain syndrome and signs of root damage

Results and discussion

We studied the results of observations of 165 patients with lumbar pain who were treated in the hospital of the Tashkent Medical Academy, a multidisciplinary clinic, and the neurosurgery department from 2019 to 2023.

All patients were divided into three groups according to the treatment methods, severity of the pain syndrome of lumbar osteochondrosis and the state of their somatic status.

The first group included 53 (32.2%) patients who underwent conservative treatment, blockades, physiotherapy and other methods of treatment. The second group included 55 (33.3%) patients who underwent endoscopic methods of allocating a herniated disc between the 4-5 and 5-1 sacral vertebrae of the lumbar spine. The third group consisted of 57 (34.5%) patients who underwent surgery to remove a herniated disc using an intralaminar approach.

By age, patients were distributed according to the WHO classification, which provides for the allocation of age groups: young age 14-19 years; younger middle age 20-44 years; older middle age 45-59 years; elderly age 60-74 years; old age 75-89 years; In our observations, patients were aged from 24 to 79 years.

Distribution of patients by age and gender showed that among the patients, men predominated - 116 (70.2%), and women - 49 (29.8%), which is associated with the physical exertion of men during work. Most patients 68 (41.5%) of older middle and old age, the maximum number of patients fell on the age group of 60-74 years, 50 (30.4%), which is consistent with the data of world scientists.

When examining the somatic status, it was revealed that among 165 patients, 67 (40.5%) patients had somatic pathology, manifested in the form of arterial hypertension in 51 (31.0%) patients, ischemic heart disease in 13 patients (7.8%). In 18 (11.2%) cases

diabetes mellitus was noted, in 4 (2.6%) patients liver pathology and in 1 (0.9%) renal failure. It should be noted that in one and the same patient a combination of two or more somatic diseases was noted, this was especially typical for cardiovascular diseases.

In our studies, 112 (67.8%) of 165 patients underwent surgical treatment, the indications for surgical treatment were: cauda equina syndrome with increasing dysfunction of the pelvic organs and radiculo-ischemic manifestations; duration of radicular pain syndrome or pain in the lumbar region for at least 4 weeks; herniated disc of any localization, but only at one level, confirmed by MRI with axial sections; lack of effect from conservative treatment.

Neurological symptoms in the second and third groups in total 173 cases, they could combine several symptoms at once in one patient in both groups. The most frequent complaint presented by patients in the second and third groups was pain in the lumbar spine (38 cases), the second most frequent complaint was gait disturbance and sensory disturbance (36 cases each), the third most frequent complaint was a forced body position due to pain syndrome (27 cases).

Analysis of the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail in the study of 165 patients showed the following results, twice as much observation at the level of LV-SI 106 (64.3%) compared to LIV-LV 59 (35.7%), this is due to the greatest load on the lumbar spine associated with a low-mobility sacrum.

Positive results among the 165 patients studied were noted in 156 (95.6%), without changes in 9 (5.4%). The indicators in all 3 groups were good since a differentiated approach to the treatment of patients with lumbar pain is always justified.

This proves the effectiveness of treatment methods for patients with lumbar hernias with a differentiated approach.

A study of the quality of life of 165 patients was achieved using the European Quality of Life Questionnaire EuroQol-5D and a visual analogue scale (VAS) to determine the intensity of the pain syndrome.

In all the study groups, the most significant deterioration of the EuroQol-5D questionnaire parameters was pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression. The study of the quality of life (QOL) of patients in all groups was conducted before and after surgical treatment.

Analysis of the results of the study of the quality of life (QOL) of 165 patients showed that the data obtained in all three groups were different, the deterioration of the QOL indicators of the first group did not differ much from normal, in the second group it was revealed that the QOL indicators of patients moderately worsened, in the third group this indicator of the QOL of patients worsened greatly and slowly recovered, this is due to the course of the disease and degenerative changes in osteochondrosis of the spine with concomitant somatic pathology.

Descriptors pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression deviated from the norm to a greater extent in the second and third groups and slowly recovered, the QOL indicators of patients in the first group returned to normal immediately after surgical

treatment. A study of 165 patients showed that the QOL parameters pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression suffer the most, which is facilitated by the emotional state of patients.

Pain syndrome as a strong irritant primarily affects the emotional state of patients, being a provoking factor in the deterioration of the QOL of patients.

For a full assessment of the QOL of patients, it is necessary to use two or more questionnaires covering more impaired descriptors and indicators. To study the parameters of pain syndrome, we used a scale (VAS) for the completeness of the study.

VAS scores before surgery revealed mild pain (1-3 points) in 20 (37.7%) patients in the first group, moderate pain (4-6 points) in 7 (13.2%), mild pain in 21 (38.2%) patients in the second group, moderate pain in 33 (60%), very severe pain (7-9 points) in one patient, unbearable pain (10 points) in one patient, mild pain in 6 (11%) patients in the third group, moderate pain in 42 (73.6%), very severe pain in 8 (14%), and unbearable pain in 1 (2%) patients.

After surgery, pain syndrome regressed to the point of disappearance in all three groups, mild pain persisted only in two patients in the first group, one patient in the second group, and four patients in the third group, which proves the effectiveness of treatment methods with a differentiated approach.

The visual scale and its five parameters allow a more detailed examination of the pain syndrome, no pain (0 points), mild pain (1-3 points), moderate pain (4-6 points), very severe pain (7-9 points), unbearable pain (10 points), which means the maximum possible version of the sensation of pain syndrome.

Thus, the restriction of movement, the inability of patients to engage in everyday work sharply reduces social existence and adaptation in the living environment. A long process of rehabilitation and pain syndrome exhausts the nervous system in most patients, causing emotional even after the disorder and depressive syndrome, which persists for a long time even after recovery.

Conclusions:

1. Distribution of patients by age and gender showed that among the patients, men predominated, there were 116 (70.2%), and women - 49 (29.8%), which is associated with the physical exertion of men during work. The majority of patients 68 (41.5%) were of middle and old age, the maximum number of patients fell on the age group 60-74 years, 50 (30.4%), which is consistent with the data of world scientists.

2. Analysis of the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail in the studied 165 patients showed the following results, twice as many observations at the level of LV-SI 106 (64.3%) compared to LIV-LV 59 (35.7%), this is due to the greatest load on the lumbar spine associated with a low-mobility sacrum

3. When examining the somatic status, it was revealed that among 165 patients, 67 (40.5%) patients had somatic pathology, manifested in the form of arterial hypertension in 51 (31.0%) patients, ischemic heart disease in 13 patients (7.8%). In 18 (11.2%) observations, diabetes mellitus was noted, in 4 (2.6%) patients, liver pathology, and in 1 (0.9%), renal failure.

4. The most frequent complaint presented by patients of the second and third groups was pain in the lumbar spine 38 cases, the second most frequent complaint was gait disturbance and sensory disturbance 36 cases each, the third most common complaint was a forced body position due to pain syndrome 27 cases.

5. Positive results among the 165 patients studied were noted in 156 (95.6%), unchanged in 9 (5.4%). The indicators in all three groups were good since a differentiated approach to the treatment of patients with lumbar pain is always justified.

References

- Aleksanyan M. M. et al. / The role of infectious agents in the etiopathogenesis of degenerative diseases of the intervertebral discs: scientific publication // Spinal surgery - Novosibirsk, - 2020. - Vol. 17 N 2. - P. 23-30.
- Aslanukov M. N. et al. / Lumbar microdiscectomy using intraoperative ultrasound: scientific publication // Surgery. Pirogov Journal - Moscow, - 2020. - N 2. - P. 21-31.
- Baykov E. S., Baikalov A. A. / The relationship between biomechanical and biochemical parameters of the spinal motion segments and recurrence of lumbar intervertebral disc herniations: scientific publication // Spinal surgery. - Novosibirsk. 2017. - Vol. 14 N4. - P. 61-68.
- Basankin I. V. et al. / Comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of transpedicular endoscopic sequestrectomy and microdiscectomy in the treatment of lumbar intervertebral hernias with a high degree of migration: scientific publication // Journal of Neurosurgery named after N. N. Burdenko - Moscow. - 2020. - Vol. 84 N 6. - P. 15-25.
- Voronina D. D. [et al.] / General magnetic therapy in the rehabilitation of patients after surgical treatment of intervertebral disc herniations: scientific publication // Issues of balneology, physiotherapy and therapeutic physical education. - Moscow, - 2017. - Vol. 94 N2. - P. 24-28.
- Gospod A. O. et al. / Characteristics of pain syndrome in patients with discogenic pathology at the lumbosacral level in the preoperative period: scientific publication // Bulletin of Traumatology and Orthopedics named after N. N. Priorov - Moscow, 2017. - N2. - P. 32-39.
- Dreval O. N. et al. / Pathogenetic aspects and risk factors for the development of recurrence of lumbar disc herniation: a literature review: scientific publication // Spinal surgery - Novosibirsk, 2021. - Vol. 18 N 1. - P. 47-52.
- Evsina O. V. Quality of life in medicine is an important indicator of the patient's health status (literature review) // Electronic scientific journal "Personality in a changing world: health, adaptation, development": 2013. No. 1. - P. 119-133.
- Kononov N. A. et al. / Experience of using percutaneous endoscopic discectomy in the treatment of patients with degenerative diseases of the lumbosacral spine: scientific publication // Journal of Neurosurgery named after N. N. Burdenko. - Moscow. 2017. - Vol. 81 N5. - P. 56-62.

10. Kochkartaev S. S. et al. / Dynamics of the microelement composition of intervertebral discs in herniated lumbar spine: scientific publication // Bulletin of the Association of Doctors of Uzbekistan. - ISSN 2010-7773. - 2020. - N 4. - P. 50-53.
11. Kravtsov M. N. / Historical aspects of video endoscopic surgery of the lumbar spine: scientific publication // Surgery of the spine - Novosibirsk. 2021. - Volume 18 N 1. - pp. 70-77.
12. Chao-Yuan G., Ding-Jun H., Liang Y., Le-Qun Sh., Qin-Peng Z., Bao-Rong H., Hao H. / Intradural Lumbar Disc Herniation: A Case Report and Literature Review // Clin Interv Aging. 2019 Dec 23;14: 2295-2299. doi: 10.2147/CIA.S228717. e Collection 2019.
13. Cuihua Y., Baojun W., Hongkuan L. / Cuihua Yuan Clinical Analysis of Minimally Invasive Percutaneous Treatment of Severe Lumbar Disc Herniation with UBE Two-Channel Endoscopy and Foraminal Single-Channel Endoscopy Technique // Oxid Med Cell Longev. 2022 Oct 13;2022: 9264852. doi: 10.1155/2022/9264852. E Collection 2022.
14. Hao-Wei J., Cheng-Dong C., Bi-Shui Z., Yong-Li W., Pan T., Xue-Sheng J. / Unilateral biportal endoscopic discectomy versus percutaneous endoscopic lumbar discectomy in the treatment of lumbar disc herniation: a retrospective study // J Orthop Surg Res. 2022 Jan 15;17(1):30. doi:10.1186/s13018-022-02929-5.
15. Hiroaki M., Fumitake T., Kazuta Y., Kosuke S., Yoshihiro I., Yoichiro Takata, Toshinori S., Toru M., Koichi S. / Operating Costs of Full-endoscopic Lumbar Spine Surgery in Japan // Neurol Med Chir (Tokyo). 2020 Jan 15;60(1):26-29. doi:10.2176/nmc.oa.2019-0139. Epub 2019 Oct 17. 16. Matthew J. M.G., Mohamad B., Kristin R. A., Clinton J. Devin M / An analysis from the Quality Outcomes Database, Part 1. Disability, quality of life, and pain outcomes following lumbar spine surgery: predicting likely individual patient outcomes for shared decision-making // J Neurosurgery Spine Volume 27 October 2017; 357-367.
17. Pravesh S.G., Biswadji S.H., Jantijn A., Job van S., Steven K., Maurits van T., Wilco C.P., Vleggeert-Lankamp C., Sidney M.R. / Percutaneous Transforaminal Endoscopic Discectomy Versus Open Microdiscectomy for Lumbar Disc Herniation: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis // Spine (Phila Pa 1976). 2021 Apr 15;46(8):538-549. doi: 10.1097/BRS.0000000000003843.
18. Quanlai Z., Liang X., Zhongxuan W., Chen L., Yu Z. / Comparison of the efficacy of fully endoscopic spine surgery using transforaminal and interlaminar approaches in the treatment of prolapsed lumbar 4/5 disc herniation // J Orthop Surg Res. 2022 Aug 13;17(1):391. doi:10.1186/s13018-022-03282-3.